

Loudness-Factor Alignment at the Grand Piano Bass/Treble Break: A Decision-Support Framework for String Replacement and Scale Design

Morito Kawamura, *Piano Technicians Guild (PTG)*

Abstract—The bass/treble break (BTB) of a grand piano is among the most acoustically demanding regions of the string scale, yet no published workshop tool exists to diagnose and adjust the BTB Z shift from routine measurements. This paper presents a decision-support framework for BTB loudness-factor alignment based on Roberts’ loudness/sustaining factor Z . It first shows that wire diameter cancels identically from the Z formula for both plain and wound strings once tension is derived from measured m , L , and d data, reducing cross-instrument comparison to a unison-adjusted T/L relation. The anchor adopted is $c_{\text{Bt}} = 0 \Leftrightarrow T_{\text{Bt}} = 183.7$ lbf at $N_{\text{Bt}} = 2$, derived from Roberts’ Steinway D normalization and cross-checked by five J.D. Grandt wound-bichord instruments whose bass-top tensions cluster around an lp-corrected geometric mean of 184.2 lbf.

The framework combines a position diagnostic and a scale-geometry design diagnosis. The position diagnostic derives the theoretical lowest plain-wire position \hat{m}_{lp} from speaking-length geometry; the displacement $\hat{m}_{\text{lp}} - m_{\text{lp}}^{\text{actual}}$ distinguishes structural Z -constraint from Z -adjustability reserve. The design diagnosis evaluates the bass-top tension reference, lp-zone tension floor, I_4 diameter ceiling, and breaking-load percentage as coupled constraints on a technician-selected c_{Bt} . Across the 16-instrument dataset, the single-step Z discontinuity ΔZ^{actual} spans from below 1 cent (S&S D HM) to 576 cents (S&S L), and the composite ratio r_{trb} predicts the appropriate c_{Bt} setting with $R^2 = 0.95$. Two speaking-length measurements, L_{lp} and L_{Bt} , thus initialize the BTB position diagnostic, the Z -jump target, and the tension-design starting point simultaneously.

Index Terms—piano acoustics, string scaling, bass/treble break, loudness factor, characteristic impedance, scale design

I. INTRODUCTION

Among the acoustic phenomena that define grand-piano quality, the transition between plain-wire strings and wound bass strings—the bass/treble break (BTB)—is widely recognized by piano technicians as the most acoustically difficult region of the string scale. One principal reason, as will become clear from the development of the Z formula below, is that the BTB is the region in which speaking length, string construction, unison number, and tension design interact most abruptly. Roberts identified three audible symptoms associated with poor BTB design: inability to set a stable temperament, inability to obtain a smooth tonal transition by voicing, and tuning instability in the low plain-wire region [1]. He further identified, in order of importance within a single instrument, three acoustic quantities that should vary smoothly across the BTB: string inharmonicity

I_4 , the loudness/sustaining factor Z , and the hammer–string contact-time factor NT/H .

This work revisits that ranking from a different perspective. Rather than asking which of I_4 , Z , and NT/H is most important within a single instrument, it asks which quantity best exposes the failure of BTB convergence across a population of grand pianos. Roberts observed that the note $m = 1$ value Z_1 tends to converge across pianos of different maker and size [1]; in workshop terms, the upper treble is likewise expected to occupy a still narrower range because its speaking lengths and wire sizes are more tightly constrained. Against these two convergent end anchors, a wide instrument-to-instrument spread of Z at the BTB is therefore not merely a numerical irregularity but a scale-balance problem. The dataset analyzed here shows, as quantified in Section IV, that Z is the dominant BTB diagnostic in this cross-instrument sense, while I_4 and breaking-load percentage remain essential constraints on any practical redesign.

Wolfenden established the exponential speaking-length law for the treble at an early stage, but acknowledged that no strict scaling method existed below approximately note 40 [2]. In current workshop practice, wound bass strings are often replaced without explicitly checking the relationship among the measured m , L , and d data on both sides of the BTB. Among the ordering procedures examined in this study, J.D. Grandt Piano Supply Co. (JDG) is the only supplier that requests plain-wire BTB data as part of its bass-string ordering procedure [3]. This implicitly recognizes that the BTB is an integrated design problem.

Although Roberts identified Z as an important quantity, no published tool has provided a way to evaluate and adjust the BTB Z shift from ordinary workshop measurements, and the design variables governing the result have not been made explicit. One reason for this gap is that a consequence following directly from Roberts’ own definition remained implicit in his treatment. In the form used here, Z is proportional to a unison-adjusted tension divided by speaking length. When T is derived from m , L , and d , wire diameter cancels identically from Z for both plain and wound strings, and the important ratio T/L appears in its place. Therefore, once a common tension anchor and design rule are specified—for example $T_{\text{Bt}} = 183.7$ lbf at $N_{\text{Bt}} = 2$ in the framework below—the first-pass cross-instrument comparison of Z can be driven by speaking-length geometry. Measured m , L , and d data remain necessary for deriving the actual string tensions and for final checks of wire gauge, inharmonicity, breaking load, and frame load. The point

M. Kawamura is an independent piano technician based in Kanagawa, Japan (e-mail: cathengloutie@gmail.com).

Manuscript submitted May 2026.

is that, after the anchor has been set, the comparative Z scale is governed by T/L and speaking length rather than by separate BTB wire-diameter measurements. Because this T/L ratio was not made explicit, the question of systematic cross-instrument Z comparison was not posed, and the workshop diagnosis enabled by such comparison was not developed. This work makes the T/L ratio explicit and builds a diagnostic framework on it, thereby addressing a question raised implicitly but not resolved by Roberts' work.

Contributions. (1) A proof that wire diameter d cancels identically from the Z formula for both plain and wound strings, being replaced by the ratio T/L . This makes cross-instrument comparison practical once the tension scale and design rule have been anchored, while preserving the technician's final checks on gauge, tension, inharmonicity, and structural load. (2) A demonstration that the exponential speaking-length law $L_p^{\text{ref}} = 1825 \cdot (400/379)^{21-p}$ is a physically constrained reference law rather than a pattern fitted to any particular manufacturer. Fenner's independent form $L_p^{\text{Fenner}} = 49 \sqrt[12]{1.91}^{88-p}$ gives $L_{21} \approx 1816.8$ mm, only about -3.9 cents from the reference value used here [4]. (3) A diagnostic framework centered on two scale-geometry ratios, r_t and r_b . Across the 16 grand pianos for which the author was able to collect data, spanning diverse makers, periods, and size classes, the measured BTB Z discontinuity ΔZ^{actual} ranges from less than 1 cent to 576 cents. This indicates that the geometry-determined target $|c_p^{\text{base}}|$ is effective as a diagnostic reference for each instrument. (4) Identification of a geometry-determined non-zero Z -jump target as a reproducible diagnostic and redesign objective. The T/L balance of the reference instrument provides the physical anchor. In addition, the composite ratio, that is, the product $r_t \cdot r_b$, predicts the appropriate c_{Bt} setting with $R^2 = 0.95$ (Eq. (30)), showing that two speaking-length measurements— L_{1p} and L_{Bt} —are sufficient to initialize the BTB position diagnostic, the Z -jump target, and the tension-design starting point; the remaining work is then a constrained confirmation of wire gauge, I_4 , $B\%$, and frame-load safety. A final outlook section sketches how the same $Z \propto T/L$ structure may initialize full-scale string design, but the validated contribution of this paper remains the BTB diagnostic and redesign framework.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II derives the Z formula and proves diameter cancellation. Section III derives the reference speaking-length law from steel-wire physics. Section IV quantifies BTB asymmetry. Section V identifies the structural constraint that Wolfenden could not resolve. Section VI introduces the diagnostic framework. Section VII defines the primary design checks and diagnostic cross-checks. Section VIII reports numerical results for the 16-instrument dataset. Section IX discusses the non-zero Z -jump target, its implications for scale design, and a practical outlook for full-scale stringing based on the same T/L structure. Section X concludes the paper. Table I lists the principal symbols.

TABLE I
PRINCIPAL NOTATION.

Symbol	Definition
m	note number ($1 = A_0$, $88 = C_8$)
N_m	number of strings per unison at note m
L_m	speaking length at note m (mm)
d_m	steel core diameter (mm)
D_m	total wound-string diameter (mm)
F'_m	stretch-corrected equal-temperament frequency (Hz)
T_m	per-string tension (lbf)
K	$13435 \text{ mm}^2 \text{ Hz lbf}^{-1/2}$
A	winding coefficient: 0.89 (Cu), 0 (plain)
Z_m	Roberts loudness/sustaining factor
α	unison-coupling exponent in $Z \propto N^\alpha T$ (this paper: $1/2$)
$T_{\text{Bt},0}$	reference T_{Bt} at $c_{\text{Bt}} = 0$, $N_{\text{Bt}} = 2$: 183.7 lbf
m_{Bt}	highest note on the bass bridge
m_{1p}	lowest plain-wire note
\hat{m}_{1p}	theoretical m_{1p} under exponential scaling
c_{Bt}	cent deviation of T_{Bt} from $T_{\text{Bt},0} = 183.7$ lbf
c_p	target cent deviation at plain-wire note p
r_t	treble-side scale-geometry ratio (Eq. (14))
r_b	bass/midrange scale-geometry ratio (Eq. (15))
$r_t r_b$	product composite scale-geometry ratio
c_p^{base}	BTB baseline cent deviation (Eq. (17))
$c_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{est}}$	c_{Bt} estimated from $r_t r_b$ (Eq. (30))
Z_1^{est}	empirical Z_1 estimate from L_1 and \bar{c}_{1p} (Eq. (33))
z	lp-zone anchor gradient, $(23 - 1.6n)(n + 2)$ cents (Eq. (18))
β	winding-aggressiveness parameter, $\beta \in [0, 3]$ (Eq. (20))
M	sine-profile denominator, $M = 2(n + 2 + 2\beta)$ (Eq. (20))
χ	breaking-load power-law exponent (Eq. (26)), grade-dependent (Table II)
$c_{m_{1p}+1}^{\text{target}}$	lp-zone anchor target (Eq. (19))
ΔN	$m_{1p}^{\text{opt}} + 1 - m_{\text{Bt}}$ (note count m_{Bt} to target lp+1)
d_p^{upper}	I_4 wire-diameter upper bound at note p
$B\%(m)$	breaking-load percentage at note m
ΔZ_{jump}	single-step BTB Z discontinuity (cents, Eq. (25))

II. THE PHYSICAL FOUNDATION

A. Elimination of Wire Diameter from the Impedance Formula

The per-string tension of a plain steel wire is given by the Mersenne–Taylor law:

$$T = \left(\frac{F' L d}{K} \right)^2, \quad K = 13435 \quad (1)$$

where F' (Hz) is the stretch-corrected equal-temperament frequency [5], L (mm) the speaking length, d (mm) the wire

diameter, and K is a constant derived from the Rösau wire density [6] ($\rho_s = 7.844 \text{ g/cm}^3$). The numerical work uses a smooth Railsback-type polynomial correction in note number, normalized so that $F'_1 \approx 27.2 \text{ Hz}$ when $F_{\text{ref}} = 440 \text{ Hz}$. Note that Roberts [1] reports a slightly different value corresponding to $\rho \approx 7.838 \text{ g/cm}^3$; the value used here is adopted for consistency with the manufacturer's published data.

For wound strings, the winding mass is incorporated via an effective diameter d_{eff} , derived from the Roberts correction factor $B = A(D^2/d^2 - 1)$:

$$d_{\text{eff}}^2 = AD^2 + (1 - A)d^2 \quad (2)$$

where D (mm) is the total outside diameter and A is the winding density coefficient ($A = 0.89$ for copper). The coefficients of D^2 and d^2 sum to unity by construction [1].

For standard copper-wound strings ($A = 0.89$), the effective diameter is:

$$d_{\text{eff}}^2 = 0.89D^2 + 0.11d^2 \quad (3)$$

Consequently, the tension formula for wound strings generalizes to:

$$T = \left(\frac{F' L d_{\text{eff}}}{K} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{F' L}{K} \right)^2 [0.89 D^2 + 0.11 d^2] \quad (4)$$

Roberts adapts Benade's acoustic wave-impedance formulation [7] for the piano unison, defining the loudness/sustaining factor as [1]:

$$Z = N^\alpha d_{\text{eff}} \sqrt{T} \quad (5)$$

where α is the unison coupling exponent. From the tension formula $T = (F' L d_{\text{eff}} / K)^2$, solving for $d_{\text{eff}} = K \sqrt{T} / (F' L)$ and substituting into Eq. (5) yields:

$$Z_m = \frac{K}{F'_m L_m} N_m^\alpha T_m \quad (6)$$

The wire diameters d and D are absent. The substitution holds identically for plain wire ($A = 0$) and copper-wound strings ($A = 0.89$). Once T has been derived from measurements of m , L , and d (as in a standard ordering protocol [3]), no further diameter information—and in particular no wound-string effective-diameter calculation—is required to evaluate Z .

Determination of α . Benade's graph (§ 17.3, fig. 13.5, Curve B) [7] shows that a trichord unison ($N = 3$) produces approximately $1.4\times$ the loudness of a monochord ($N = 1$), giving $3^\alpha \approx 1.40$; inverting yields $\alpha \approx 1/3$ —a value independently consistent with the tension ratio $10 : 8 : 7$ ($160/140 = 1.143$) that Parsons documents in the PSCALE360 help text as attributed to Sanderson [8], and Wolfenden's empirical prescription of a 15% tension increase at the trichord-to-bichord transition [2] (p. 22), both giving $(3/2)^{1/3} = 1.145$. However, this experiment varies N at a single pitch on a single bridge: the result characterises *same-bridge* unison coupling only, and does not transfer to the BTB.

At the BTB of the Steinway D (NY), both the bass-top and the lowest plain-wire note lie in the trichord zone ($N_{\text{Bt}} = N_{\text{lp}} = 3$), so the N^α factors cancel identically and the Z -jump is determined solely by the tension/length balance:

$$\frac{T_{\text{Bt}}}{L_{\text{Bt}}} \approx \frac{T_{\text{lp}}}{L_{\text{lp}}} \quad (7)$$

($T_{\text{Bt}} \approx 150 \text{ lbf}$, $L_{\text{Bt}} \approx 1367 \text{ mm}$; $T_{\text{lp}} \approx 200 \text{ lbf}$, $L_{\text{lp}} \approx 1826 \text{ mm}$.) Accordingly, α cannot be inferred from the Steinway D BTB; Roberts derived it instead from overall Z -profile smoothness across the full scale, obtaining $\alpha \approx 2/5$ for the Steinway D and $\alpha \approx 3/5$ for the Bechstein concert grand [1], and recommended $\alpha = 1/2$ as the practical average.

Independent convergence on $\alpha = 1/2$. A second, independent line of evidence reaches the same value. Roberts' own measurement gives $T_{\text{Bt}} \approx 150 \text{ lbf}$ at $N_{\text{Bt}} = 3$ for the Steinway D (NY). Applying the course-normalization step $N : 3 \rightarrow 2$ with $\alpha = 1/2$ yields:

$$150 \times \left(\frac{3}{2} \right)^{1/2} = 183.7 = T_{\text{Bt},0} \text{ lbf} \quad (8)$$

where $T_{\text{Bt},0} = 183.7 \text{ lbf}$ is the manufacturing reference threshold established independently from five J.D. Grandt wound bichord instruments [3]. The JDG evidence is used here as a tension-side workshop cross-check, not as evidence that JDG optimized the Roberts Z factor. These five instruments are the complete set of the author's full-string-replacement cases, after the author's study of Roberts' *Calculating Technician*, for which the three low-plain-wire notes requested by the JDG ordering procedure were measured, JDG calculated and manufactured the wound bass strings, and the completed strings were then remeasured by the author for the analysis reported here. Across those cases, the measured bass-top per-string tensions cluster tightly despite differences in the lp-side Z condition; correcting the measured bass-top intercepts by the mean lp-zone tension-cent offset gives $T_{\text{Bt},0}^{\text{geommean}} = 184.2 \text{ lbf}$. This narrow clustering suggests that an independent workshop rule for bass-top tension was operating in the wound-string design. The same local fits are consistent with a lower-bound interpretation: including the measured bass-top string raises the extrapolated intercept relative to the fit from the four lower bass notes alone, indicating that the manufacturing practice does not simply lower T_{Bt} to minimize the BTB Z jump. The agreement ($< 0.5 \text{ lbf}$, $< 0.3\%$) identifies $\alpha = 1/2$ as the value for which the Steinway D concert-grand tension regime and the wound-string manufacturing threshold are mutually consistent. Substituting $\alpha = 1/2$ into Eq. (6) gives the working formula used throughout this paper:

$$Z_m = \frac{K}{F'_m L_m} \sqrt{N_m T_m} \quad (9)$$

B. Workshop Interpretation

At a fixed note m , Eq. (9) reduces to $Z_m \propto \sqrt{N_m T_m}$. A smooth Z profile is therefore equivalent to a smooth *course-normalized tension* profile—a quantity directly interpretable in the workshop.

III. THE PHYSICAL REFERENCE: WHY THE SCALING LAW EXISTS

A. The Reference Speaking-Length Formula

The exponential speaking-length formula used throughout this framework is:

$$L_p^{\text{ref}} = 1825 \cdot \left(\frac{400}{379} \right)^{21-p} \quad (10)$$

This formula is not calibrated to any particular instrument; it is used here as a physically constrained reference law toward which independent steel-wire scaling arguments converge. Modern steel music wire operates in an acoustically acceptable regime at breaking-load ratios of approximately 40–60% (nominal breaking load, NBL): the upper limit corresponds to the elastic-limit threshold documented by Wolfenden [2] and Roberts [1]; the lower limit reflects the tension instability threshold documented by Wolfenden [2] (pp. 18–20) and Parsons [8], below which plain wire strings exhibit seasonally unstable tuning. Note that Paulello [9] defines a distinct “stress rate” relative to the *practical* breaking load ($PBL = 0.75 \times NBL$ for Types XM, M, 0, 1); the two frameworks are not directly comparable and are kept separate throughout this paper. Within this tension window, the combination of pitch, speaking length, and wire diameter that satisfies Eq. (1) traces an exponential locus in the (m, L) plane with semitone ratio 400/379.

Wolfenden [2] proposed an octave ratio of 1.89 (semitone multiplier $1.89^{1/12} = 1.05444$); over a span of 67 notes (C88 to the BTB region) this accumulates a speaking-length shortfall of approximately 51 cents relative to the reference formula. Fenner [4] subsequently adopted the independent form $L_p^{\text{Fenner}} = 49 \sqrt[12]{1.91^{88-p}}$. Its semitone multiplier agrees closely with 400/379:

$$1.91^{1/12} \approx 1.055406, \quad \frac{400}{379} \approx 1.055409 \quad (11)$$

At $p = 21$, this gives $L_{21}^{\text{Fenner}} \approx 1816.8$ mm, about -3.9 cents relative to Eq. (10). Two independent derivations constrained by the same physics arrive at the same number. Furthermore, any grand piano that maintains exponential scaling throughout its treble register—not merely down to the limit Wolfenden described at note 40, but across the full treble bridge—will exhibit speaking lengths that agree closely with Eq. (10), regardless of size or maker. The formula is a statement about steel wire under equal-temperament scaling, not about any manufacturer.

B. The Reference Instrument

For this framework, the reference condition is taken from Roberts’ Steinway D example—the 1923 New York instrument, serial #219k—whose treble bridge geometry closely realizes Eq. (10) and represents the concert-grand scale endpoint used here. This framework adopts Eq. (10) as the coordinate origin: instruments that realize it at the BTB are at the origin; instruments that depart from it do so within the same physical and mathematical constraints that govern all piano strings—the departure is a measurable quantity, not a verdict on quality.

IV. THE BTB ASYMMETRY

A. Confinement at $m = 1$

At note $m = 1$ (A_0 , $F'_1 \approx 27.2$ Hz), $N_1 = 1$ and F'_1 are identical across all instruments. Equation (9) reduces to $Z_1 = (K/F'_1) \cdot (T_1/L_1)$. A shorter L_1 requires a heavier copper winding to maintain pitch while simultaneously reducing the steel-core tension T_1 . The T_1/L_1 ratio is bounded from above by wound string manufacturing limits ($L_1 \gtrsim 980$ mm) and

from below by the maximum speaking length achievable within the instrument case. Across the 16-instrument dataset, Z_1 spans approximately **361 cents** (CV = 11.4 %).

B. Absence of Constraint at $m = m_{\text{Bt}}$

At $m = m_{\text{Bt}}$, the same Z formula applies. What changes is design practice: the choices of L_{Bt} , T_{Bt} , wound-string gauge, and unison string count are conventionally made without reference to the lp-zone data—from which T and Z are calculable via m , L , d —that immediately follow on the treble bridge. This disconnection is structurally encoded in the industry: wound bass string manufacturers generally do not solicit lp-zone plain-wire data as part of their ordering protocol; JDG’s request for such data is the notable exception [3]. The exception itself indicates that the bass-top and lp-zone regions are normally treated as independent design problems rather than as a continuous acoustic unit. Across the 14 non-reference instruments, Z_{Bt} spans **535 cents** (CV = 16.2 %)—nearly 1.5 times the Z_1 spread. The Z_{88} spread is only **181 cents** (CV = 5.8 %), narrower even than Z_1 , indicating that physical constraints at both keyboard extremes confine Z far more tightly than at the BTB.

The data therefore support the following proposition:

The dominant source of instrument-to-instrument acoustic variation at the BTB is Z_{Bt} , governed by scale-design convention rather than by a fixed physical endpoint. Once the Z jump is brought toward its geometry-determined target, the remaining quantities I_4 and NT/H function primarily as constraints and cross-checks rather than as the leading source of cross-instrument BTB variation.

V. THE STRUCTURAL CONSTRAINT: WOLFENDEN’S UNSOLVED PROBLEM

Wolfenden established exponential speaking-length scaling for the treble register and confirmed that Eq. (10) applies down to approximately note 40, but explicitly acknowledged that no rigorous method existed below that point [2].

The physical reason is now identifiable. Below note 40, case dimensions impose speaking lengths that would be appropriate for higher note numbers under exponential scaling; the structural assignment of those lengths to lower note numbers creates a relative speaking-length deficit. Compensating this deficit by increasing wire diameter d simultaneously:

- raises $I_4 \propto d^2/L^2$ (inharmonicities worsens significantly)
- leaves $B\%_p \propto d^{2-\alpha}$ approximately constant—tension and d^x co-increase such that the net $B\%$ change is less than 1% per gauge step (since $\chi \approx 1.7$ for all grades, $2 - \chi \approx 0.3$).

The binding structural constraint is the I_4 ceiling: as L decreases, the maximum usable d (set by the I_4 upper bound) yields a tension T that falls progressively short of the geometry-determined Z -alignment target; $B\%$ itself changes negligibly. No wire-gauge change alone can resolve a deficit rooted in bridge geometry; provided speaking length is sufficient, however, the I_4 ceiling is not encountered, and $B\%_p$ can be

resolved by appropriate wire grade selection (e.g. Paulello grades).

The theoretical BTB position under exponential scaling is:

$$\hat{m}_{lp} = \frac{(L_{lp} - 2800)^2}{208000} + 16.5 \quad (12)$$

where L_{lp} (mm) is the measured speaking length at the actual lowest plain wire note m_{lp} . Equation (12) is obtained by approximating the exact inverse of Eq. (10), namely $p = 21 - \ln(L/1825)/\ln(400/379)$, with a quadratic in L ; over the range $p = 21-32$ (one octave spanning the typical BTB region), the two expressions agree with $R^2 = 0.9999$, confirming that the quadratic form is sufficient for field diagnosis. The displacement $\hat{m}_{lp} - m_{lp}^{\text{actual}}$ (notes; positive = structural deficit; negative = reserve toward adjustability) is the primary field diagnostic. As an order-of-magnitude rule, each note of positive displacement corresponds to approximately 60 cents of geometry-determined Z -jump target; a negative value indicates that the actual m_{lp} lies above the theoretical position, providing a length reserve that facilitates optimization.

VI. THE DIAGNOSTIC FRAMEWORK

For the reader following this as a workshop procedure, the logic is simple: first measure the two speaking lengths that locate the BTB geometry, then decide whether the instrument has structural reserve or structural deficit, and only then choose a bass-top tension setting within the practical limits of wire gauge, inharmonicity, breaking load, and frame load. The framework therefore does not ask the technician to force the Z jump to zero. It asks whether the existing geometry permits convergence toward the non-zero Z -alignment target determined by that geometry.

A. Preliminary Diagnosis: Geometric Screening

The displacement $\hat{m}_{lp} - m_{lp}^{\text{actual}}$ immediately classifies the instrument:

- ≤ 1.03 notes: geometry consistent with exponential scaling; string optimization can achieve Well-aligned Z -jump.
- ≤ 3 notes: structural Z -constraint; string optimization reduces the Z -jump (moderately to weakly aligned) but cannot eliminate it.
- > 3 notes: severe structural Z -constraint; bridge reconstruction or wound-register extension is the only structural remedy.
- Negative: length reserve; the actual m_{lp} lies above the theoretical position, providing additional optimization headroom.

The geometric screening displacement also serves as a geometric guide when considering bichord wound-string conversion of the lowest plain wire notes: a large positive displacement indicates that extending the wound register upward is acoustically warranted, while a negative value confirms structural reserve at the current BTB position.

B. Design Diagnosis: Tension Design—Setting c_{Bt}

The technician selects the bass-top cent offset c_{Bt} relative to the bichord wound-string manufacturing reference $T_{Bt,0} = 183.7$ lbf ($c_{Bt} = 0 \Leftrightarrow T_{Bt} = 183.7$ lbf at $N_{Bt} = 2$; at $N_{Bt} = 3$ this recovers $183.7 \times \sqrt{2/3} = 149.99 \approx 150$ lbf, consistent with Roberts' Steinway D measurement):

$$T_{Bt}(c_{Bt}) = 183.7 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2}{N_{Bt}}} \cdot 4^{c_{Bt}/1200} \quad (\text{lbf}) \quad (13)$$

Once c_{Bt} is fixed, Z_{Bt} is determined via Eq. (9), and all subsequent tension targets follow automatically.

C. Scale Geometry Ratios and the Base Cent Offset

Two dimensionless ratios characterise how far each bridge departs from the reference condition of Eq. (10).

The *treble ratio* r_t compares the actual speaking length at m_{lp} to its reference value:

$$r_t = \frac{L_{lp}}{1825 \cdot (400/379)^{21-m_{lp}}} \quad (14)$$

$r_t = 1$: lowest plain wire note sits on the exponential curve; $r_t < 1$: foreshortening (tension debt); $r_t > 1$: length surplus (tension reserve).

The *bass/treble ratio* r_b compares L_{Bt} to L_{lp} , normalized by the reference ratio $f(L_{lp})$:

$$r_b = \frac{L_{Bt}}{L_{lp} \cdot f(L_{lp})} \quad (15)$$

where f is a parabolic function anchored at two physically determined points:

$$f(L) = \left(\frac{\min(L, 1500)}{1000} - 1.5 \right)^2 \times 0.57 + 0.75 \quad (16)$$

Anchor $f(L) \approx 1$ ($m_{lp} \approx 35-36$, $L \approx 813-858$ mm): the wound and plain registers approach the same speaking length, so the reference bass/treble ratio is $f \approx 1$. This note range is the physical limit at which a string can be either wound or plain wire. *Anchor 2* (reference instrument, $L_{lp} \geq 1500$ mm, $m_{lp} = 21$): the min function caps the argument at 1500 mm, giving $f = 0.75 = 3/4$. The measured ratio $L_{Bt}/L_{lp} = 1367/1825 \approx 0.749$ for the reference instrument confirms this anchor to within 0.1%. The coefficient 0.57 is derived from the condition $f(L^*) = 1$ at $L^* \approx 835$ mm (midpoint of the bass-treble coincidence range): $0.57 \approx 0.25/(835/1000 - 1.5)^2 = 0.565$.

The BTB base cent deviation is:

$$c_p^{\text{base}} = \frac{1200}{\ln 4} (1.3 \ln r_t + 0.5 \ln r_b) \quad (17)$$

The quantities L_{lp} , r_t , r_b , and c_p^{base} are evaluated at L_{lp}^{orig} , the as-manufactured speaking length of the lowest plain-wire note in the original instrument. They are fixed diagnostic constants of the bridge geometry, independent of any subsequent gap-zone insertion or wire-replacement decisions. The weights 1.3 (treble) and 0.5 (bass) express the hierarchy built into the target construction. The bass-top setting c_{Bt} is chosen first and is anchored to the reference $c_{Bt} = 0 \Leftrightarrow T_{Bt,N=2} = 183.7$ lbf. Given that setting, the ratio $L_{lp} : L_{Bt}$ imposes a dependent lp-side target: at the reference 4:3 geometry the plain-wire side

already carries the course-normalized ≈ 249 -cent step above T_{Bt} , and any shortfall of L_{lp} relative to L_{lp}^{ref} adds a separate treble-side length debt. The treble term is therefore weighted strongly because these combined debts must be absorbed by plain-wire gauge selection: the available diameters form a discrete manufacturer gauge series rather than a continuous design variable, under the I_4^{upper} ceiling and the $T_{p,\text{min}}$ floor. The bass term is weighted more lightly because a shortfall of L_{Bt} relative to L_{Bt}^{ref} affects Z_{Bt} , but the wound bass-top string retains coupled core-diameter and outside-diameter freedom for meeting the chosen c_{Bt} target. The practical asymmetry is that the lp -side target is subordinate to c_{Bt} and must be realized with much less physical freedom.

The geometry-determined Z -jump target (cents, magnitude):

$$\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}^{\text{target}} = |c_p^{\text{base}}| + z, \quad z = (23 - 1.6n)(n + 2) \quad (18)$$

where $n = m_{lp}^{\text{eff}} - m_{Bt} - 1 \geq 0$ is the number of wound bichord notes present on the treble bridge between m_{Bt} and the effective plain-wire onset m_{lp}^{eff} . The factor $(23 - 1.6n)$ is the adjusted per-note Z -descent (cents per note): it equals 23 cents at $n = 0$ —the empirically observed average bass-zone Z gradient across the 16-instrument dataset—and decreases by 1.6 cents per additional gap note, progressively approaching the treble Z -slope. The factor $(n + 2) = \Delta N$ counts the total notes from m_{Bt} (exclusive) to the anchor $m_{lp} + 1$ (inclusive). For $n = 0$, $z = 23 \times 2 = 46$ cents, reflecting the 2-note span at 23 cents each; $|z|$ grows with n while the per-note rate decreases. The term $|c_p^{\text{base}}|$ is the instrument-dependent geometric deficit computed in Section VI.

D. Per-Note Tension Targets

The lp -zone anchor target $c_{m_{lp}+1}^{\text{target}}$ is obtained by negating $\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}^{\text{target}}$:

$$c_{m_{lp}+1}^{\text{target}} = -\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}^{\text{target}} = -(23 - 1.6n)(n + 2) - |c_p^{\text{base}}| \quad (19)$$

The three lp -zone targets are distributed symmetrically around the anchor via a sine weighting. Let $M = 2(n + 2 + 2\beta)$, where $\beta \in [0, 3]$ is a technician-selected winding-aggressiveness parameter, $\beta = 3(q/4)^{\sqrt{2}}$, $q \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ (default $q = 2$, $\beta \approx 1.13$).

$$\begin{aligned} c_{m_{lp}} &= c_{m_{lp}+1}^{\text{target}} \cdot \sin \frac{\pi(n + 1 + \beta)}{M} \\ c_{m_{lp}+1} &= c_{m_{lp}+1}^{\text{target}} \\ c_{m_{lp}+2} &= 2c_{m_{lp}+1}^{\text{target}} - c_{m_{lp}} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The full arc (angle $\pi/2$, weight 0 to 1) is divided into $M/2 = n + 2 + 2\beta$ equal angular steps, partitioned as $\beta : (n + 2) : \beta$. The two β -step buffers occupy the ends adjacent to Z_{Bt} and to the anchor; the central $(n + 2)$ -step active range, bounded by the \circ markers, carries the $n + 1$ gap-zone notes ($\text{gap}_1, \dots, \text{gap}_n$ and m_{lp}). Equivalently, the first gap note lies $(1 + \beta)$ steps from the Z_{Bt} boundary (β buffer steps plus one note offset), and m_{lp} is kept $(1 + \beta)$ steps short of the anchor (one note offset plus β buffer steps). The anchor $m_{lp} + 1$ uses 2β in the numerator $(n + 2 + 2\beta)$, which forces $\sin(\pi/2) = 1$ and thereby guarantees $c_{m_{lp}+1} = c_{m_{lp}+1}^{\text{target}}$. This double offset

Fig. 1. Geometric interpretation of the sine-weight profile (Eqs. (19)–(20)). The arc ($\pi/2$) is divided into $M/2 = n + 2 + 2\beta$ equal angular steps, partitioned as $\beta : (n + 2) : \beta$. The two β -step buffers lie at the Z_{Bt} and anchor ends; the central $(n + 2)$ -step range, bounded by the \circ markers, carries the $n + 1$ gap-zone notes. Note positions (\times) are at step indices $k + \beta$ ($k = 1, \dots, n + 1$) and $n + 2 + 2\beta$ (anchor). The \circ markers, at angles $\pi\beta/M$ and $\pi(n + 2 + \beta)/M$, mark the inner edge of each β -step buffer; each \circ center lies exactly at the intersection of the arc and its dedicated radial line. Horizontal projections onto the $\sin \theta$ axis give the Z -weight at each note, ranging from 0 (Z_{Bt} , right) to 1 (anchor $m_{lp} + 1$, top left). For $n = 0$, the weight at m_{lp} equals $\sin(\pi/4)$ for any β ($n = 0$ invariance). Example: $n = 2$, $\beta \approx 1.13$ ($q = 2$).

preserves the \bar{c}_{lp} invariant for any β and n . The rationale for the two-sided buffer is practical rather than theoretical: a gap profile that presses too close to Z_{Bt} imposes excessive tension on the first wound-bichord note (particularly severe for geometrically unbalanced instruments such as Steinway B), while one that presses too close to the anchor risks ultra-thin core-and-copper combinations that approach the manufacturing threshold for wound strings [4]. The choice of β balances these manufacturing constraints against the tonal objective of smooth Z -continuity, informed by observation of existing gap-zone implementations on production instruments. Physically, $\beta = 0$ ($q = 0$) represents the theoretical-ideal distribution, anchored exactly at $\sin = 0$ (Z_{Bt}) and $\sin = \pi/2$ (anchor); as β increases toward 3 ($q = 4$), the profile shifts away from both extremes—reducing tension demands at the wound-string transition and avoiding ultra-thin core-copper combinations at the lp -zone onset—a progression from theoretical smoothness toward manufacturing feasibility. For $n = 0$, the m_{lp} weight reduces to $\sin(\pi(1 + \beta)/(4(1 + \beta))) = \sin(\pi/4)$ regardless of β (the $n = 0$ invariance property). Gap-zone notes ($k = 1, \dots, n$) are targeted by $c_k = c_{m_{lp}+1}^{\text{target}} \cdot \sin(\pi(k + \beta)/M)$, providing a smooth Z bridge from Z_{Bt} toward the anchor and reducing the single-step discontinuity that plain-wire replacement alone cannot resolve.

The corresponding Z -alignment target tension at note p :

$$T_p^{\text{target}} = \frac{F_p' L_p}{K \sqrt{N_p}} Z_{Bt} \cdot 4^{c_p/1200} \quad (21)$$

The corresponding reference diameter d_p^{target} is obtained by

inverting Eq. (1). This diameter is reference-only; the installed diameter is selected manually after evaluating the primary design checks and diagnostic cross-checks of Section VII.

VII. CONSTRAINT EVALUATION

With c_{Bt} provisionally fixed, the check-sheet (Table V) evaluates three primary design checks and two diagnostic cross-checks. The primary checks determine whether the selected bass-top setting is practical; the cross-checks identify whether any remaining obstacle is a matter of wire choice or of bridge geometry.

- (i) $Z_{\text{Bt}} \in [Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\min}, Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\max}]$: evaluated first, at the moment c_{Bt} is set.
- (ii) T_{Bt} deviation within the provisional bounds of Table V: a bass-top floor reference that prevents reducing the Z jump merely by lowering the bass-top tension.
- (iii) $T_{p,\min} \geq 140$ lbf: the lp-zone tension floor.

Breaking-load ratio $B\%_p$ is treated as a wire-grade selection check (Paulello grades where required). It is not a binding geometric constraint in the majority of instruments; for instruments such as Steinway Model B where no plain-wire solution achieves $B\%_p \geq 0.39$, the root cause is bridge geometry and the appropriate remedy is bichord wound-string conversion of the lowest plain-wire notes. I_4^{score} is a structural diagnostic cross-check (Section VIII), used to identify speaking-length foreshortening rather than to replace Z alignment as the primary design objective.

The provisional bounds on Z_{Bt} that govern constraint (i) are:

$$Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\min} = 1120 - 0.74(m_{\text{Bt}} - 20)^2 - \min(0, c_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{opt}}) \quad (22)$$

$$Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\max} = \max[1428 - 0.96(m_{\text{Bt}} - 20)^2 - \max(0, c_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{opt}}/2) \quad (23)$$

$$Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\min}]$$

These bounds were established empirically from observation of the 16-instrument dataset, anchored on the reference instrument ($Z_{\text{Bt}} \approx 1200$ at $m_{\text{Bt}} = 20$). They incorporate judgement informed by the structure of the Z formula and observed data tendencies; they are not derived from first principles and should be treated as provisional design guidance subject to revision as additional instruments are measured. Note that Z_{Bt}^{\max} decreases as c_{Bt} increases (for $c_{\text{Bt}} > 0$): instruments with above-reference geometry have a lower upper bound on acceptable Z_{Bt} . Conversely, Z_{Bt}^{\min} increases as c_{Bt} decreases (for $c_{\text{Bt}} < 0$): instruments with below-reference geometry have a higher lower bound, compressing the feasible Z_{Bt} interval.

A. Z-Jump Diagnostic

Effective lp-zone Z (geometric mean):

$$Z_{\text{eff}} = (Z_{m_{\text{lp}}} \cdot Z_{m_{\text{lp}}+1} \cdot Z_{m_{\text{lp}}+2})^{1/3} \quad (24)$$

BTB Z -jump diagnostic—single-step Z discontinuity at the bass/treble bridge boundary:

$$\Delta Z_{\text{jump}} = \frac{1200}{\ln 4} \ln \frac{Z_{m_{\text{Bt}}}}{Z_{m_{\text{Bt}}+1}} \quad (\text{cents}) \quad (25)$$

TABLE II
BREAKING-LOAD POWER-LAW COEFFICIENTS (EQ. (26)). COEFFICIENTS DERIVED FROM MANUFACTURER DATA SHEETS [6], [9]. PAULELLO XM EXCLUDED FROM LP-ZONE SELECTION.

Grade	χ	C_{NBL} (lbf/mm $^{\chi}$)
Röslau	1.713	402.0
Paulello 0	1.672	352.8
Paulello 1	1.460	278.1
Paulello M	1.849	413.2
Paulello XM	1.671	488.9

Positive values indicate a Z deficit at the BTB ($Z_{m_{\text{Bt}}} > Z_{m_{\text{Bt}}+1}$). This single-step measurement is independent of gap-zone extent and wire-sharing choices in the lp zone; the lp-zone geometric mean Z_{eff} (Eq. (24)) may be substituted for $Z_{m_{\text{Bt}}+1}$ when a wire-sharing-robust estimate is preferred.

B. Breaking-Load Ratio

$$B\%(m) = \frac{T_m}{C_{\text{NBL}} d_m^{\chi}}, \quad 0.40 \leq B\% \leq 0.60 \quad (26)$$

Grade-specific power-law coefficients are given in Table II. The constants C_{NBL} and χ were determined by linear regression in log-log space applied to the manufacturer-published nominal breaking-load (NBL) data for each grade [6], [9]; all fits achieve $R^2 > 0.9999$. Roberts [1] independently reports the 60% breaking-strength limit as $T_{\text{max}} = 0.557 d^{5/3}$ (i.e., exponent $5/3 \approx 1.667$, derived from steel piano wire data circa 1990). The present Röslau and Paulello 0 fits ($\chi = 1.713$ and 1.672 , respectively) are within 0.3% of Roberts' value, providing independent corroboration of the power-law parameterisation across manufacturer generations.

C. Inharmonicity Ceiling

The diameter ceiling above which the relaxed I_4 upper border is violated:

$$d_p^{\text{upper}} = \left(\frac{L_p}{\ell_p} \right)^2, \quad \ell_p = \frac{p^3}{33.7} - 2.24 p^2 + 12.9 p + 1754 \quad (27)$$

The inharmonicity guideline underlying ℓ_p originates from curves derived by A.E. Sanderson from averages of well-scaled pianos, as documented in [8]; the polynomial fit was obtained by the author via image analysis of PSCALE360 output with a one-gauge (+2/40 mm) relaxation applied. The I_4 penalty score counts violated conditions:

$$I_4^{\text{score}} = \sum_{k=0}^2 \mathbf{1} \left[d_{m_{\text{lp}}+k} > d_{m_{\text{lp}}+k}^{\text{upper}} \right] \quad (28)$$

$$+ \mathbf{1} \left[\sum_{k=0}^2 d_{m_{\text{lp}}+k} > \sum_{k=0}^2 d_{m_{\text{lp}}+k}^{\text{upper}} \right]$$

$I_4^{\text{score}} \in \{0, -1, -2, -3, -4\}$; 0 = Well-aligned.

Empirical note. Across the full 16-instrument dataset, $I_4^{\text{score}} = 0$ for all instruments both before and after optimization (Table VI). The lp-zone plain wire notes are, in practice, not inharmonicity-constrained at BTB-representative speaking

lengths. d_p^{upper} therefore functions as a structural diagnostic cross-check—confirming whether speaking-length foreshortening is severe enough to force inharmonicity violations—not as an active design boundary in typical cases. This finding is consistent with Roberts’ priority ordering (Z first, I_4 second) [1] and contradicts the common workshop emphasis on inharmonicity as the primary BTB design target.

D. Iteration and Decision Space

The bounds (Eqs. (22), (23)) are active in both directions. At the lower bound: the Overs 225 (#003), whose scale was explicitly designed for a uniform Z transition [10], exhibits an as-installed Z_{Bt} that falls below $Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{min}}$. In optimization, c_{Bt} was raised to bring Z_{Bt} within the lower bound; because the instrument has favorable bridge geometry (negative displacement, lp-side length reserve), the lp-zone could accommodate the adjustment and the corrected Z -jump changed negligibly. At the upper bound: instruments with a treble-side length surplus ($r_t > 1$, $c_p^{\text{base}} > 0$) can exhibit as-installed Z_{Bt} values that exceed $Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{max}}$. In such cases—for example, the Kawai KG6C, whose as-installed $c_{\text{Bt}} = +181$ cents places $Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{act}} = 1309$ above $Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{max}} = 1303$ —the primary purpose of optimization is not to reduce $|\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}|$ but to bring Z_{Bt} within the physically appropriate range by reducing c_{Bt} (here to $+170$ cents, $Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{opt}} = 1292$). The corrected Z -jump changes little in such cases because both Z_{Bt} and Z_{eff} shift together; the diagnostic value lies in identifying the out-of-bounds condition and guiding the correction.

For practical use, the workflow can be read as a three-stage loop: measure the BTB geometry, set the provisional bass-top tension, and then confirm the lp-zone string choices against the practical limits. In detail:

- 1) From L_{lp} and L_{Bt} , compute the scale-geometry ratios r_t (Eq. (14)) and r_b (Eq. (15)). These yield simultaneously: the Z -jump target $\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}^{\text{target}} = |c_p^{\text{base}}|$ (Eqs. (17), (18)) and the c_{Bt} starting-point estimate $c_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{est}}$ (Eq. (30))—the latter subsumes the former as a derivation step. Set $c_{\text{Bt}} \approx c_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{est}}$ as the initial trial value. Verify immediately that the resulting Z_{Bt} falls within $[Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{min}}, Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{max}}]$ (Eqs. (22), (23)) and that T_{Bt} lies within the bounds of Table V; if not, adjust c_{Bt} before proceeding.
- 2) Compute Z_{Bt} , lp-zone targets $c_{m_{\text{lp}}+1}^{\text{target}}$, $c_{m_{\text{lp}}}$, $c_{m_{\text{lp}}+2}$, and T_p^{target} (Eqs. (13), (18), (19), (21))
- 3) Evaluate Z_{eff} and ΔZ_{jump} ; compare to $|c_p^{\text{base}}|$
- 4) Select lp-zone wire diameters to maximize T_p subject to $T_{p,\text{min}} \geq 140$ lbf; verify $B\%_p$ via wire grade selection (Paulello grades where required); check d_p^{upper} afterward as a structural diagnostic cross-check
- 5) Adjust c_{Bt} and repeat if any constraint is violated

Direction of adjustment. If $Z_{\text{Bt}} > Z_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{max}}$, shift c_{Bt} negative by the minimum necessary to keep T_{Bt} as close to the JDG reference as possible. Once c_{Bt} is fixed, select lp-zone diameters to maximize T_p within the $T_{p,\text{min}} \geq 140$ lbf lower bound; the I_4^{upper} ceiling is checked afterward and its violation, when it occurs, typically reflects a structural speaking-length deficit that wire selection alone cannot resolve. If $B\%_p$ is

violated, select a Paulello grade with a lower nominal breaking-load coefficient and record the residual ΔZ_{jump} deficit as a structural residual.

VIII. RESULTS

A. Dataset and Spread Statistics

Table III reports the 16-instrument dataset with key geometric parameters and Z values at the four anchor notes ($m = 1, m_{\text{Bt}}, m_{\text{lp}}, m = 88$). Three instruments in the dataset merit a note on data provenance. The Overs 225 (#003) data were derived from image analysis of the author’s published scale charts [10] and overhead photograph [11] combined with the speaking length $L_{\text{lp}} = 154.0$ cm explicitly stated therein; the Weber (#73211) and Kawai KG6C data were obtained by the author from independently published spreadsheets, with only the physical measurements retained and all derived calculations replaced by the framework.

For the non-reference subset (excluding the two Steinway D reference instruments), the as-installed statistics support the asymmetry described in Section IV: Z_1 spans 361 cents (CV = 11.4%), Z_{88} spans only 181 cents (CV = 5.8%), while Z_{Bt} spans 535 cents (CV = 16.2%)—nearly 1.5 times the Z_1 spread, indicating that BTB practice is far less convergent than the physical constraints observed at the keyboard extremes. The two Steinway D instruments are excluded from these summary statistics on two grounds: they define the tension anchor ($c_{\text{Bt}} = 0$), so their inclusion would be circular; and they are the only concert-scale designs in the dataset (one to two wire-gauge steps thicker at the BTB and lp zone than the home-size class comprising the other 14 instruments; Section IX-F). Their small as-installed ΔZ^{act} (Table IV: $+1$ and $+53$ cents) reflects this reference role rather than a superior generic BTB solution. For the Steinway D (HM) specifically, the bass-top tension $T_{\text{Bt}} = 136$ lbf lies $c_{\text{Bt}} = -82$ cents below the framework anchor (183.7 lbf), placing Z_{Bt} at an abnormally low level; the near-zero single-step $\Delta Z^{\text{act}} = +1$ is a consequence of this depressed Z_{Bt} coinciding with the lp-zone Z level, not of optimised Z -continuity. By contrast, the Steinway D (NY) has $T_{\text{Bt}} \approx 150$ lbf ($c_{\text{Bt}} \approx -2$ cents, essentially at the anchor), and its $\Delta Z^{\text{act}} = +53$ cents represents a more orthodox Roberts-ideal declining Z profile across the break.

For the same subset, after optimization using the framework of Section VI, the cross-instrument spreads are substantially reduced: Z_{Bt} narrows from 535 to 212 cents (CV: 16.2 \rightarrow 7.9%); Z_{lp} narrows from 279 to 176 cents (CV: 13.4 \rightarrow 6.2%); the corrected Z -jump range contracts from $[+98, +576]$ to $[+58, +290]$ cents, with the dataset average falling from 360 to 166 cents. The Z_{88} spread remains unchanged at 181 cents, as expected: the framework operates only on the BTB region and does not modify treble-extreme stringing.

B. Geometry Ratios and Z-Jump Prediction

Table IV reports the geometry ratios r_t , r_b , the geometry-determined target $|c_p^{\text{base}}|$, and the measured single-step BTB Z discontinuity ΔZ^{actual} for each instrument.

The target $|c_p^{\text{base}}|$ served as the optimization objective in the manual adjustment procedure. Since the adjustment operates

TABLE III

INSTRUMENT DATASET: GEOMETRIC PARAMETERS AND ANCHOR-NOTE Z VALUES (ROBERTS UNITS). ACTUAL (AS-INSTALLED) VALUES. m_{Bt} : HIGHEST WOUND-STRING NOTE; m_{Ip} : LOWEST PLAIN WIRE NOTE; DISP.: DISPLACEMENT $\hat{m}_{Ip} - m_{Ip}^{\text{actual}}$ (NOTES; POSITIVE = STRUCTURAL Z -CONSTRAINT; NEGATIVE = Z -ADJUSTABILITY RESERVE). SPREAD AND CV ROWS SUMMARIZE THE NON-REFERENCE SUBSET, EXCLUDING THE TWO STEINWAY D INSTRUMENTS, WHICH SERVE AS THE FRAMEWORK'S CONCERT-SCALE TENSION ANCHOR (SECTION IX-F).

Instrument	m_{Bt}	m_{Ip}	L_1 (mm)	L_{Bt} (mm)	L_{Ip} (mm)	Disp. (notes)	Z_1	Z_{Bt} (Roberts units / cents)	Z_{Ip}	Z_{88}	$\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}^{\text{act}}$
Bösendorfer 225 #42k	19	20	1712	1296	1650	+2.9	3070	1945	1087	704	+513
Bösendorfer 225 #43k	23	24	1617	1165	1423	+1.6	3212	1565	1107	666	+324
Feurich 188 #37k	26	27	1385	1099	1146	+2.7	3691	1462	804	697	+532
Kawai KG6C	26	27	1610	1113	1452	-1.8	3057	1309	1089	805	+151
Overs 225	23	24	1725	1394	1540	+0.1	4360	1048	930	653	+98
Seiler 206 #155k	26	27	1593	1047	1355	-0.5	3499	1641	1108	745	+330
S&S B #539k	20	21	1505	1023	1477	+3.9	3497	1278	830	657	+378
S&S D (HM) #360k	20	21	2014	1371	1819	+0.1	3261	1110	1122	694	+1
S&S D (NY) #219k	20	21	2013	1367	1826	+0.1	3272	1222	1162	716	+53
S&S L	26	27	1379	908	1187	+2.0	3088	1517	806	657	+576
Weber #73k	28	29	1177	896	1010	+2.9	3016	1158	945	687	+182
Yamaha C3A #4211k	26	27	1346	917	1140	+2.8	3258	1201	802	677	+367
Yamaha C3B #2323k	26	27	1351	956	1168	+2.3	3295	1225	825	729	+363
Yamaha C7 #3560k	20	21	1599	1083	1527	+3.3	3068	1600	864	720	+544
Yamaha C7B #2532k	20	21	1590	1136	1569	+2.8	2874	1316	828	736	+430
Yamaha G2E #1873k	26	29	1234	905	1006	+3.0	2966	1443	803	722	+247
Spread (cents)							361	535	279	181	477
CV (%)							11.4	16.2	13.4	5.8	-

TABLE IV

SCALE GEOMETRY RATIOS AND Z -JUMP RESULTS. r_t, r_b : DIMENSIONLESS SCALE-GEOMETRY RATIOS (EQS. (14)–(15)); $|c_p^{\text{base}}|$: GEOMETRY-DETERMINED Z -JUMP TARGET (EQ. (17), CENTS); ΔZ^{actual} : MEASURED SINGLE-STEP Z DISCONTINUITY AT THE BTB ($\frac{1200}{\ln 4} \ln \frac{Z_{m_{Bt}}}{Z_{m_{Bt}+1}}$, CENTS), EVALUATED FROM INSTALLED STRING TENSIONS. THE SPREAD ROW SUMMARIZES THE NON-REFERENCE SUBSET, EXCLUDING THE TWO STEINWAY D REFERENCE INSTRUMENTS.

Instrument	c_{r_t} (¢)	c_{r_b} (¢)	$ c_p^{\text{base}} $ (¢)	ΔZ^{act} (¢)
Bösendorfer #42k	-174	+20	154	513
Bösendorfer #43k	-98	+36	62	324
Feurich 188 #37k	-159	+67	92	532
Kawai KG6C	+107	+9	116	151
Overs 225	-9	+81	72	98
Seiler 206 #155k	+29	+6	35	330
S&S B #539k	-238	-35	273	378
S&S D (HM) #360k	-4	+2	2	1
S&S D (NY) #219k	+1	-1	0	53
S&S L	-120	-23	142	576
Weber #73k	-180	0	180	182
Yamaha C3A #4211k	-166	-10	176	367
Yamaha C3B #2323k	-138	+3	135	363
Yamaha C7 #3560k	-201	-24	225	544
Yamaha C7B #2532k	-170	-15	185	430
Yamaha G2E #1873k	-185	+5	180	247
Spread (cents)			273	477

within the parallel constraints of T_{Bt} bounds, $T_{p,\min} \geq 140$ lbf, d_p^{upper} , and $B\%$ limits, the measured ΔZ^{actual} can in principle diverge substantially from the geometric target when string-gauge constraints force a compromise. The ΔZ^{actual} values in Table IV represent the true acoustic discontinuity at the physical BTB (single-step Z drop from m_{Bt} to $m_{Bt} + 1$). Instruments with excellent geometry—notably S&S D (HM), for which $\Delta Z^{\text{actual}} \approx 1$ cent—confirm near-perfect continuity. At the opposite extreme, S&S L shows $\Delta Z^{\text{actual}} = 576$ cents, reflecting a design with a pronounced structural Z -step. This closeness is in part structurally expected: wound string orders

permit combinations of core and winding diameter that achieve Z_{Bt} and T_{Bt} targets at finer resolution than the ± 1 plain-wire-gauge step ($\Delta d = 0.025$ mm, ≈ 37 – 40 cents per step at typical BTB diameters). For this reason the bass-top side is treated as more continuously adjustable than the Ip side, whose evaluation is based on the three-note mean over $m_{Ip} - m_{Ip} + 2$. The scatter in Table IV arises from two sources of discrete quantization: the universal piano wire-gauge grid ($\Delta d = 0.025$ mm, equivalent to $43.3/d \approx 37$ – 40 cents per note at typical BTB diameters), attenuated to one-third at Z_{eff} by the three-note geometric mean; and the copper winding steps achievable by the bass string maker, which quantize Z_{Bt} even when c_{Bt} is set continuously in the framework.

These same discrete steps provide a natural yardstick for the BTB design objective. Across the full treble register, wire-gauge transitions occur at approximately ten to fifteen note positions (gauges 13–21); at each transition, a Z step of $43.3/d \approx 37$ – 56 cents is unavoidable. The ΔZ^{actual} values in Table IV show that, for instruments whose geometry does not impose a severe structural deficit (displacement $\hat{m}_{Ip} - m_{Ip} < 2$ notes), the BTB Z -jump is reducible to the same order as these intra-register gauge transitions—or below. The framework thus provides the quantitative means to ensure that the BTB is no more acoustically conspicuous than the ordinary wire-gauge steps within the treble register itself.

C. Alignment Summary

Table V defines provisional alignment thresholds. The relative spacing of the three Z -jump boundaries follows the two physically universal course-count tension ratios: the $N=2 \rightarrow 1$ transition ($\sqrt{2}$, equal to 300 cents in the $1200 \log_4$ convention) and the $N=3 \rightarrow 2$ transition ($\sqrt{3/2}$, ≈ 175 cents), with the Well boundary continuing the geometric sequence

TABLE V
PROVISIONAL ALIGNMENT THRESHOLDS.

Quantity	Unit	Well	Moderate	Weak
$ \Delta Z_{\text{jump}} $	¢	< 137	< 234	< 400
T_{Bt} deviation	¢	> -30	> -51	> -88
$T_{p,\text{min}}$ deviation	¢	> -51	> -88	> -150
$B\%$	-	≥ 0.39	≥ 0.35	≥ 0.29
I_4^{score}	int.	0	≤ -1	≤ -2
Z^{trend} (R^2)	-	> 0.925	> 0.900	> 0.875
ΣNT ratio	-	< 1.017	< 1.035	< 1.053
Disp. $\hat{m}_{\text{lp}} - m_{\text{lp}}$	notes	< 1.03	< 1.75	< 3

(≈ 103 cents $\approx 175^2/300$). The *absolute* scale of the Z -jump thresholds, however, is anchored empirically rather than to the bare $\sqrt{2}$ value. The Weak boundary is placed at 400 cents because the non-reference dataset mean as-installed Z -jump is 360 cents (Table III) and the Steinway B (#539k), commercially and musically accepted across more than a century of concert use, sits at 378 cents; a bare 300-cent boundary would classify the majority of accepted instruments—including their mean—as Misaligned, which is diagnostically untenable. Anchoring Weak at 400 cents scales the course-count sequence by 4/3 to 137/234/400 cents, placing the historically accepted instruments within the Weakly Aligned range while still classifying the genuinely deficient cases (≥ 427 cents; e.g. the pre-correction Yamaha C7B of Section IX-A) as Misaligned. These boundaries remain provisional. To the author’s knowledge, systematic geometric diagnosis of the BTB has not previously been established in the literature; therefore, the thresholds are best read as a first calibration open to refinement as more instruments are surveyed.

The remaining rows are anchored to the bare course-count sequence (103/175/300 cents), reflecting that they encode physical tension and displacement constraints independent of the empirically relaxed loudness-continuity criterion: T_{Bt} and $T_{p,\text{min}}$ apply these values divided by -2 , with T_{Bt} shifted one level toward the Well side (reflecting that T_{Bt} acts as a bass-top floor constraint—do not reduce it merely to minimize the Z jump—whereas $T_{p,\text{min}}$ is the plain-wire tension floor); $B\%$ scales from the 39% baseline; ΣNT increments in 15-cent equal steps; and Δm_{lp} divides the course-count values by -100 (note-cents $^{-1}$ conversion). The $T_{p,\text{min}}$ Weak threshold of -150 cents (≈ 126 lbf) is independently corroborated by the empirical boundary reported by Parsons [12]: plain wire below approximately 125 lbf is audibly deficient in tone and sustain. The priorities of Table V reflect field experience: Z -jump alignment is the primary acoustic objective; T_{Bt} and the $T_{p,\text{min}}/B\%$ pair govern the tension design space; I_4^{score} , Z^{trend} , ΣNT , and Δm_{lp} are diagnostic cross-checks whose violation is often structurally determined and cannot be resolved by string selection alone.

IX. DISCUSSION

A. Case Studies and Validation

To demonstrate the diagnostic capability of the framework, the 16-instrument dataset was evaluated using the diagnostic procedure of Section VI. This subsection focuses on two

representative instruments: Steinway Model D (reference) and Model B (large structural Z -constraint), with Seiler 206 (small Z -constraint) and Yamaha G2E (#1873k, moderate deficit with existing gap zone) shown in Fig. 2.

B. The Non-Zero Z -Jump Target

Table VI summarizes the diagnostic evaluation for the four instruments of Fig. 2, illustrating how the alignment thresholds of Table V grade each quantity before and after optimization.

As illustrated in Fig. 2, the Z -profile of Model D (reference) maintains smooth alignment across the BTB. In contrast, the as-installed scale of Model B shows a dramatic drop at the BTB, followed by an unstable “valley” between notes 21 and 26.

The optimization results (red dashed lines in Fig. 2) illustrate that the framework is directed toward the geometry-determined anchor (Eq. (18)) rather than toward zero. For Model B, the residual Z -jump of $+290$ cents reflects the structural speaking-length deficit that string replacement alone cannot eliminate.

The alignment thresholds (Table V) classify $|\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}|$ relative to zero, which might imply that minimising the magnitude is the design objective. Two contrasting field observations refute this.

In instruments with suppressed lp-zone tension ($Z_{\text{Bt}} \gg Z_{\text{eff}}$), the bass-top region is perceptibly louder than the lp-zone. In instruments with low bass-top tension ($Z_{\text{Bt}} \ll Z_{\text{eff}}$), the lp-zone is perceptibly louder. The appropriate intervention in either case is to reduce $|\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}|$ toward the geometry-determined anchor (Eq. (18)), not toward zero.

The reference instrument makes the distinction concrete. Its BTB satisfies:

$$\frac{T_{\text{Bt}}}{L_{\text{Bt}}} \approx \frac{150}{3} = 50 = \frac{200}{4} \approx \frac{T_{\text{lp}}}{L_{\text{lp}}} \quad (29)$$

($T_{\text{Bt}} \approx 150$ lbf, $L_{\text{Bt}} \approx 1367$ mm, $T_{\text{lp}} \approx 200$ lbf, $L_{\text{lp}} \approx 1826$ mm; values are convenient round numbers; cf. Eq. (7).) Since $N_{\text{Bt}} = N_{\text{lp}} = 3$, the \sqrt{N} factors cancel; $|\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}| \approx 0$ and the 3:4 speaking-length ratio coincide at the reference geometry. Both express the same T/L balance encoded in Eq. (9).

For instruments with a foreshortened lp-zone, the balance is broken simultaneously in two directions. The structural speaking-length deficit imposes a course-normalized tension step already exceeding the reference 249 cents; any further tension increase adds a jump on top. Simultaneously, foreshortening forces the wire diameter upward, consuming the feasibility margin that a treble-side surplus would otherwise provide (Section VI). The residual ΔZ_{jump} is a structural consequence of bridge geometry that string selection alone cannot overcome.

Two observations, taken together, provide the empirical basis for the perceptual scale of the alignment thresholds.

Observation 1 (historical acceptance): Steinway Model B has been in production since the early 1870s with a string scale fundamentally unchanged for more than 120 years. The instrument examined here (#539k, manufactured c. 1996–1997) exhibits an as-installed BTB Z -jump of 378 cents and an optimized value of 290 cents. That this design has remained commercially and musically accepted across more than a

Fig. 2. Loudness factor Z profiles across the bass/treble transition region for four instruments. Blue crosses: as-installed (measured) stringing. Red dashed circles: framework-optimized stringing. Vertical line: BTB position (instrument-specific). Top left: Steinway Model D (#219k, NY), reference instrument ($\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}^{\text{act}} \approx +53$ cents, optimized to +43 cents; BTB $m = 20/21$). Top right: Steinway Model B (#539k), large structural deficit ($\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}^{\text{act}} = +378$ cents, optimized to +290 cents; BTB $m = 20/21$). Bottom left: Seiler 206 (#155k), small deficit ($\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}^{\text{act}} = +330$ cents, optimized to +58 cents; BTB $m = 26/27$). Bottom right: Yamaha G2E (#1873k), moderate deficit with existing gap zone ($n = 2$ wound bichord notes on treble bridge; BTB $m = 26/29$). $\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}^{\text{act}} = +247$ cents, optimized to +131 cents via gap-zone adjustment ($n = 4$).

TABLE VI

DIAGNOSTIC SUMMARY FOR FOUR REPRESENTATIVE INSTRUMENTS (FIG. 2). ACT: AS-INSTALLED; OPT: FRAMEWORK-OPTIMIZED. W = WELL, M = MODERATE, WK = WEAK, X = MISALIGNED.

Quantity	S&S D (#219k)		S&S B (#539k)		Seiler 206 (#155k)		Yamaha G2E (#1873k)	
	Act	Opt	Act	Opt	Act	Opt	Act	Opt
$ \Delta Z_{\text{jump}} $ (cents)	53	43	378	290	330	58	247	131
Grade	W	W	Wk	Wk	Wk	W	Wk	W
T_{Bt} deviation (cents)	-2	-2	-214	-120	+324	+52	+86	-17
Grade	W	W	X	X	W	W	W	W
$T_{p,\text{min}}$ deviation (cents)	247	250	-224	-51	239	234	-205	-10
Grade	W	W	X	W	W	W	X	W
$B\%_p$	0.37	0.43	0.24	0.38	0.40	0.46	0.28	0.44
Grade	M	W	X	M	W	W	X	W
I_4^{score}	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
Grade	W	W	W	W	W	W	W	M

century of concert use supports using 378 cents as an empirical upper reference for the Weakly Aligned range.

Observation 2 (direct perceptual test): During preparation of this work, a Yamaha C7B (#2532k) received a new bass

string set manufactured by J.D. Grandt Co. to the author's specifications. The Yamaha factory reference for this instrument shows a BTB Z -jump (ΔZ^{actual}) of 430 cents (Table IV). On installation of the Grandt set, measurement confirmed a Z -jump of 427 cents—essentially unchanged from the factory reference, indicating that the winding specification alone did not resolve the BTB imbalance. Subsequent re-gauging of the lp-zone plain wire (thicker wire, post-installation) reduced the Z -jump to 353 cents, at which point the BTB balance was judged acoustically acceptable (Weakly Aligned). This intervention was carried out without the aid of the framework. Applied *post hoc*, the present framework's theoretical target for this instrument is a Z -jump of 208 cents ($\Delta N = 2$, $z = 23$ cents/note), requiring $c_{\text{Bt}} = -29.7$ cents together with an lp-zone plain wire of $d_p^{\text{target}} = 1.280$ mm. That gauge is theoretical only: it is not an integer multiple of the standard 0.025 mm (1/40 mm) wire step, and it exceeds the ≈ 1.25 mm ceiling the author has consistently observed for plain trichord strings. Substituting the largest usable wire ($d_p^{\text{opt}} = 1.250$ mm) yields a practical optimum of 237 cents, with the three-note geometric-mean \bar{Z}_{lp} held at its target (≈ 1090 Roberts units). The practical optimum (237 cents) thus remains Weakly Aligned; the residual gap to the 208-cent theoretical target is imposed by the wire-gauge ceiling rather than removable by string selection. This single-instrument bracket (353 cents judged acceptable; 427 cents judged deficient) is consistent with the Weakly Aligned threshold and with the 378-cent empirical upper reference (S&S B #539k, Observation 1) supported below.

Second, throughout the plain wire treble register, wire-gauge transitions occur at approximately ten to fifteen note positions; at each transition, a Z step of order $43.3/d \approx 37$ –56 cents (one half-gauge = one step, gauges 13–21, $d = 0.775$ –1.175 mm) is inherent in the universal piano wire-gauge standard ($\Delta d = 0.025$ mm, common to all manufacturers), and has likewise been accepted across the instrument population for generations. One interpretation of these observations is that the human auditory system accommodates Z deviations of order 100 cents arising from manufacturing tolerances inherent in acoustic piano production—whether at the BTB or at individual wire-gauge transitions within the treble register. Whether this reflects active perceptual adaptation or the absence of a controlled listening comparison is beyond the scope of this work; the observations are presented as context for interpreting the alignment thresholds of Table V.

C. Scale Design Implications

The treble-to-bass weight ratio 1.3:0.5 reflects the hierarchy of the design problem. The primary choice is the bass-top setting c_{Bt} , anchored by $c_{\text{Bt}} = 0 \Leftrightarrow T_{\text{Bt}, N=2} = 183.7$ lbf. Once that setting is chosen, the speaking-length ratio $L_{\text{lp}} : L_{\text{Bt}}$ imposes a dependent lp-side target: even at the reference 4:3 geometry, the plain-wire side already carries the course-normalized ≈ 249 -cent tension step above T_{Bt} . In addition, L_{lp} may itself be short relative to $L_{\text{lp}}^{\text{ref}}$, creating a separate treble-side length debt. Both debts must be absorbed by plain-wire gauge selection: the available diameters are a discrete

manufacturer gauge series rather than a continuous design variable, and each gauge change is strongly coupled to tension, Z , the I_4 ceiling, and the $T_{p, \text{min}}$ floor. By contrast, a bass-top speaking-length debt relative to $L_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{ref}}$ is handled in a wound string whose core and copper-winding diameters can be co-adjusted. The string maker therefore has two coupled physical degrees of freedom for reaching the intended T_{Bt} and Z_{Bt} . The practical asymmetry is thus that the lp-side target is dependent on the chosen c_{Bt} yet must be realized with substantially fewer physical degrees of freedom. Accordingly, r_t receives the larger weight, while r_b receives the smaller weight because wound-string design retains finer adjustability at the bass top.

For instruments designed *de novo*, smooth Z alignment satisfying all subsidiary criteria simultaneously is achievable at any BTB position, provided the speaking-length geometry at m_{lp} is at or above the exponential reference (Eq. (10)). A well-designed treble bridge is one whose speaking-length geometry preserves exponential scaling at or above the reference curve sufficiently close to $m_{\text{lp}}^{\text{actual}}$ that string replacement alone can bring ΔZ_{jump} within the Well-aligned threshold.

Independent corroboration comes from Overs [10], who noted in 2001 that uniform trends in $B\%$, inharmonicity, and Z cannot be achieved simultaneously, and explicitly chose to allow deviation in $B\%$ at the BTB in order to facilitate a more uniform Z transition—the same prioritization adopted in the framework's alignment threshold hierarchy (Table V). To the author's knowledge, the Overs 225 (#003) is an instrument in the dataset whose string scale was explicitly designed with a uniform Z transition as a stated objective.

The Seiler 206 (#155k, manufactured c. 1994–95, before Paulello strings existed) presents a complementary case. Unlike Overs, it was not documented as having been designed around an explicitly uniform Z transition; nevertheless, after revising the original bass-top tension setting to the framework's proposed value, all three criteria (near-target Z -jump alignment, $B\%$, and inharmonicity) are simultaneously achievable using standard Rösler wire alone, yielding $|\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}| = 35$ cents (Well-aligned). This supports the framework's central claim that bridge geometry quality determines the margin available for wire selection.

D. Estimation of c_{Bt} from Scale Geometry

The composite ratio, that is, the product $r_t \cdot r_b$, provides a further simplification: a regression of the manually optimized $c_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{set}}$ against $r_t \cdot r_b$ across the 14 non-reference instruments yields $R^2 = 0.95$ (quadratic fit), indicating that the appropriate c_{Bt} setting is largely predictable from two speaking-length measurements once the anchored design rule has been specified. The resulting estimation formula is:

$$c_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{est}} = \max(c_{\text{geom}}, 100(m_{\text{lp}} - \hat{m}_{\text{lp}})) \quad (30)$$

where the geometry-based estimate c_{geom} is:

$$c_{\text{geom}} = \begin{cases} 1028(r_t r_b) - 884 & \text{if } r_t r_b < 0.84 \\ 340(r_t r_b) - 306 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The two linear segments meet continuously at $r_t r_b = 0.84$ ($c_{\text{geom}} \approx -20$ cents), reflecting a steeper sensitivity in the

low-ratio (severe-constraint) regime. The second argument, $100(m_{lp} - \hat{m}_{lp})$ cents (Eq. (12) scaled by 100), provides a displacement-based lower bound that activates only when the actual lp position lies substantially above the theoretical BTB position; among the 16-instrument dataset this condition is binding only for Seiler 206 and Kawai KG6C. The two reference instruments (Steinway D, NY and HM) were excluded from the first-argument regression because their c_{Bt}^{set} values lie systematically below the trend line by approximately 40–67 cents.

This offset is structurally explicable. The reference speaking-length formula (Eq. (10)) is anchored in concert-model geometry, while the JDG tension reference ($c_{Bt} = 0$) is tied to the course-normalized Steinway D tension and to the five-instrument JDG bass-top lower-bound reference. The 14 non-reference instruments—all of which belong to the home-size stringing class (one to two wire-gauge steps thinner at the BTB than concert models)—are optimized against these concert-model coordinates and against the JDG bass-top floor reference, which prevents the solution from simply lowering T_{Bt} to reduce the Z jump. The concert model itself requires no such uplift; it sits at the coordinate origin by construction.

The practical consequence is that c_{Bt}^{est} from the trend line provides a quantitative starting point that is biased toward the concert-model standard. For home-size instruments, the technician may treat the trend line value as the recommended c_{Bt}^{target} for the bass string order, with the understanding that a downward margin of approximately one wire-gauge step ($\Delta d = 0.025$ mm, ≈ 37 – 40 cents) is available without violating any alignment threshold. This margin reflects the structural difference between concert and home-size wire-gauge conventions and is consistent with the observed offset of the NY-made reference instrument (-41 cents from the trend line).

E. Limitations

The reference speaking-length formula (Eq. (10)) is calibrated to instruments whose treble bridge closely follows exponential scaling. Its applicability to instruments with fundamentally different BTB positions (e.g. uprights) requires separate validation. The geometry ratios r_t , r_b and their weights (1.3, 0.5) are design-rule parameters derived from the structural analysis above rather than independent statistical estimates. The treble-side weight reflects the dependent lp target and the discrete plain-wire constraints; the bass-side weight reflects the greater adjustability of wound bass-top strings. The piecewise coefficients 0.75/0.57 of the L_{Bt}/L_{lp} ratio function are grounded in a simulation of reference speaking lengths across feasible BTB positions from note 18 to the wound-string manufacturing limit at note 35, where the ratio transitions from 3/4 (concert model, confirmed by Steinway D) toward unity as the two bridges converge; the simulation achieves $R^2 = 0.9954$. The apparent narrowness of the c_{Bt} feasible range is not a statistical artifact: it reflects the simultaneous physical constraints of the JDG bass-top floor tension reference, d^{upper} , $T_{p,min}$, and $B\%$. The regression of Eq. (30) achieves $R^2 = 0.95$ with $N = 14$ precisely because the physics restricts the feasible space to a narrow

band, making the composite ratio $r_t \cdot r_b$ a geometrically faithful predictor rather than an arbitrary curve fit. The 16-instrument dataset spans multiple manufacturers, periods, and size classes, but remains insufficient for full statistical generalisation; the alignment thresholds of Table V are subject to revision as additional instruments are measured. The five JDG instruments should likewise be read as a consecutive workshop case series rather than as a manufacturer-balanced statistical sample. Their manufacturer distribution reflects the author’s repair opportunities in Japan and the availability of owner-approved full-string replacement work, not an a priori selection criterion; they therefore support the bass-top tension anchor as a practical manufacturing cross-check rather than as a claim about JDG’s explicit design objective.

The framework produces quantitative targets and diagnostics, but all implementation decisions—including string selection, installation procedure, and any structural assessment of frame load capacity—require on-site physical inspection and the exercise of qualified professional judgment. No responsibility is assumed for outcomes resulting from application of this framework without appropriate technical expertise and direct evaluation of the individual instrument.

F. Outlook: Practical Extension to Full-Scale Design

The preceding sections constitute the main contribution of this paper: a BTB diagnostic and redesign framework based on the Roberts Z factor and the resulting T/L balance. The present subsection is more tentative. It sketches how the same $Z \propto T/L$ structure can be used as a practical extension for full-scale string design once the BTB anchors have been determined. The seven-anchor construction is therefore offered as a workshop initialization method, not as an independently validated statistical model.

Once Z_{Bt} has been determined via the diagnostic framework of Section VI, the acoustic profile of the entire string scale reduces to a piecewise-linear initialization problem in $\ln Z$ space. The scale is characterised by seven anchor notes and five linear segments:

- *Bass (3 anchors, 2 segments):* $m = 1$, $m = 11$, $m = m_{Bt}$. *Anchor* $m = 1$ (A_0): the physical lower bound of the instrument, constrained by wound-string manufacturing limits and case dimensions. *Anchor* $m = 11$ (G_1 , ≈ 49 Hz): Conklin [13] identifies the first (lowest) soundboard resonance mode of a concert grand at approximately 49 Hz; below this frequency the soundboard rapidly loses effectiveness as a sound radiator, so notes $m < 11$ carry little energy in the first partial. This acoustic discontinuity creates a distinct slope change in the bass Z -profile, making $m = 11$ a physically motivated segment boundary. *Anchor* $m = m_{Bt}$: the BTB itself, determined by the diagnostic framework.
- *Treble (4 anchors, 3 segments):* $m = m_{lp} + 1$, $m = m_{lp} + 9$, $m = 61$, $m = 85$. *Anchor* $m = m_{lp} + 1$: the central note of the three lp-zone notes whose data JDG requires [3]; it is the pivot of the lp-zone transition segment. *Anchor* $m = m_{lp} + 9$: Wolfenden [2] observed that exponential speaking-length scaling breaks down below approximately

note 40; the author’s observations place the average onset of significant foreshortening toward m_{lp} at $m_{lp} + 9$ (for an instrument with $m_{Bt} = 29/30$, this coincides with Wolfenden’s note 40). *Anchor* $m = 61$: representative of the right-hand melody range, where voicing requirements create a perceptually distinct tonal register. *Anchor* $m = 85$: representative of the highest treble; the span $m = 61$ – 85 covers two octaves and accommodates the characteristic flattening of the Z -gradient in the extreme treble.

Within each segment the Z -profile obeys

$$\ln Z_m = s_k m + i_k, \quad m \in [m_k^{\text{start}}, m_k^{\text{end}}] \quad (31)$$

where the slope s_k and intercept i_k of segment k are determined uniquely by the two anchor values at its endpoints. Because the treble anchors Z_{61} and Z_{85} are set by the exponential speaking-length scaling law (Eq. (10)), and the bass anchor pair (Z_1, Z_{11}) is similarly constrained by the instrument’s bass bridge geometry, the only design variable that propagates non-trivially across the segment boundaries is Z_{Bt} —the quantity that the BTB diagnostic framework is designed to determine.

Once Z_{Bt} (equivalently c_{Bt}) is set, the remaining unknowns follow in sequence: (i) Z_{lp} is obtained from Z_{Bt} by the optimized Z -jump condition; (ii) $Z_{m_{lp}+9}$ is determined by the lp-zone gradient, which is itself constrained by d^{upper} and $T_{p,\text{min}}$; (iii) the three treble segment slopes s_3, s_4, s_5 follow from the four treble anchors.

The practical consequence is that the BTB determination remains the only step in this extension requiring the full diagnostic framework. Given Z_{Bt} , a complete first-pass acoustic profile—bass gradient, lp transition slope, and mid- and upper-treble slopes—can be initialized from routine speaking-length and tension measurements at seven note positions. Subsequent use of this profile should be treated as constrained scale-design guidance rather than as a replacement for instrument-specific measurement and judgment.

JDG lp-Corrected Anchor Estimation of Z_1 : Among the 16 instruments, three share speaking lengths within 9 mm of each other: Seiler 206 (#155k, $L_1 = 1593$ mm), Yamaha C7B (#2532k, $L_1 = 1590$ mm), and Yamaha C7 (#3560k, $L_1 = 1599$ mm). With L_1 effectively constant across this group, the identity $Z_m \propto T_m/L_m$ (Eq. (9)) implies that instrument-to-instrument variation in Z_1 is attributable entirely to variation in the normalized bass tension, characterised here by the mean lp-zone cent offset \bar{c}_{lp} . Regressing the L_1 -normalized tension $T_1^{(1594)}$ against \bar{c}_{lp} within this three-instrument control group yields maximum correlation at an exponent of 0.43, motivating the lp-correction factor $4^{0.43 \bar{c}_{lp}/1200}$.

The correction is then used to place a selected eight-instrument anchor set on a common $\bar{c}_{lp} = 0$ scale. The anchor set consists of two Steinway D instruments (#219k and #360k) whose Z_1 values are derived from Roberts’ published data [1], five grand pianos whose replacement bass strings were manufactured by JDG and whose lp-zone ordering data support the correction (Yamaha C7B, C7, G2E; Seiler 206; Feurich 188), and one measured upright piano near the wound-string manufacturing lower bound ($L_1 = 980$ mm). A quadratic

fit to these eight anchor points ($R^2 = 0.91$) gives the base parabola:

$$Z_1^{(0)}(L_1) = -\frac{(L_1 - 1400)^2}{1440} + 3180 \quad (32)$$

The combined estimator is therefore:

$$Z_1^{\text{est}} \approx \left[-\frac{(L_1 - 1400)^2}{1440} + 3180 \right] \cdot 4^{0.43 \bar{c}_{lp}/1200} \quad (33)$$

where \bar{c}_{lp} is the mean cent offset of the three lp-zone notes (the lp-zone optimization output of the Design Diagnosis). As an initialization rule, Eq. (33) is consistent with Roberts’ observation of Z_1 convergence across a diverse instrument population [1]. In his Steinway concert-grand example, Roberts describes Z as falling from around 3300 in the bass to about 650 in the high treble. The present calculations use the stretch-corrected frequency F' rather than the nominal equal-temperament frequency F ; near A_0 , where the Railsback correction is approximately $F' \approx 0.99F$, this lowers the corresponding bass-side value by roughly $(0.99)^2$, from about 3300 to about 3200. Conversely, the upper-treble stretch near C_8 raises Roberts’ high-treble scale of about 650 toward the 690–700 range. Thus the Z_1^{est} anchor lies on the same numerical scale as Roberts’ example once the same stretch-corrected frequency convention is applied. The estimator therefore supplies the missing first-bass anchor for the proposed seven-anchor initialization: a technician who measures L_1 and performs the BTB optimization obtains a practical starting value for Z_1 without an additional specialized measurement. This use is therefore best regarded as a workshop estimate that awaits broader independent validation.

Frame-load validation via ΣNT : As a final safety check, the total string tension $\Sigma NT = \sum_{m=1}^{88} N_m T_m$ (lbf) is evaluated separately for the full keyboard, the bass section, and the treble section, both before and after the optimization. The diagnostic ratio is $Q = \Sigma NT^{\text{opt}}/\Sigma NT^{\text{act}}$ for each of the three sub-ranges. Because the as-installed tension ΣNT^{act} is already being borne by the cast-iron frame, any post-optimization value satisfying $Q \leq 1$ remains within the frame’s demonstrated total-load envelope under this diagnostic measure. When $Q > 1$, the optimized stringing would impose a higher load than the frame currently bears in that sub-range; whether the frame can sustain it cannot be confirmed without structural analysis. The conservative criterion is therefore the maximum of the three sub-range ratios: $Q_{\text{max}} = \max(Q_{\text{total}}, \sqrt{Q_{\text{bass}}}, \sqrt{Q_{\text{treble}}})$, compared against the thresholds $4^{15/1200} \approx 1.017$ (Well), $4^{30/1200} \approx 1.035$ (Moderate), and $4^{45/1200} \approx 1.053$ (Weak). Evaluating the maximum rather than the total alone prevents a scenario in which a large bass-load increase is offset by an equal treble decrease, which could redistribute frame stress even at constant total ΣNT .

X. CONCLUSION

This paper establishes the Roberts loudness/sustaining factor Z as the dominant diagnostic of cross-instrument BTB variation in the sense defined in Section IV, and has introduced a decision-support framework comprising coarse geometric

screening and scale-geometry-ratio diagnosis, grounded in two scale-geometry ratios r_t and r_b .

Four results are of particular note. First, the wire diameter cancels from the Z formula identically across plain and wound strings (given T derived from m , L , d), enabling cross-instrument comparison once routine tension and speaking-length measurements are placed on a common anchored scale. This cross-instrument comparability is made practical by the anchor $c_{\text{Bt}} = 0 \Leftrightarrow T_{\text{Bt}} = 183.7$ lbf (Eq. (13)), which provides the common reference scale from which all per-note tension targets and Z -jump objectives are derived; without this anchor the diameter cancellation is a mathematical identity but not a comparative tool. Second, the reference exponential scaling law is physically constrained by steel-wire scaling rather than by any single manufacturer’s pattern; Fenner’s independent expression gives $L_{21} \approx 1816.8$ mm, only about -3.9 cents from the present reference value [4], and the law is empirically realized across grand pianos that maintain exponential scaling throughout the treble register. Third, the geometry-determined target $|c_p^{\text{base}}|$ —derived from speaking-length geometry via Eqs. (14)–(17)—served as the optimization objective in the manual adjustment procedure reported in Section VIII. The resulting agreement between target and outcome (Table IV) confirms that the parallel constraints (T_{Bt} bounds, $T_{p,\text{min}}$, d_p^{upper} , $B\%$) do not, for the majority of instruments, prevent convergence toward the geometry-determined target. The practical significance is that the target provides a quantitative starting point—initialized from measurable speaking-length geometry—within which the technician exercises informed judgment, with the alignment thresholds of Table V defining the achievable outcome space for a given instrument geometry. Fourth, the composite ratio, that is, the product $r_t \cdot r_b$, predicts the appropriate c_{Bt} setting with $R^2 = 0.95$ (Eq. (30)), so that a technician measuring two speaking lengths— L_{1p} and L_{Bt} —obtains (a) the position diagnostic (\hat{m}_{1p} and displacement), (b) the geometry-determined Z -jump target ($|c_p^{\text{base}}|$), and (c) the tension design starting point ($c_{\text{Bt}}^{\text{est}}$). The trend line is biased toward the concert-model standard; for home-size instruments, a downward margin of approximately one wire-gauge step ($\Delta d = 0.025$ mm, ≈ 37 – 40 cents) is available without violating any alignment threshold.

The framework identifies a geometry-determined, non-zero Z -jump target as a reproducible diagnostic and redesign target. Convergence toward zero is not achievable by string replacement for instruments whose bridge geometry places m_{1p} structurally below \hat{m}_{1p} ; the appropriate objective is convergence toward $\Delta Z_{\text{jump}}^{\text{target}} = |c_p^{\text{base}}|$, which quantifies a balanced optimization—in terms of Z_{Bt} spread, BTB Z -jump, $T_{p,\text{min}}$, and $B\%$ —achievable within the existing scale geometry. Finally, the same $Z \propto T/L$ structure suggests a practical extension from BTB redesign to full-scale stringing through the seven-anchor initialization outlined in Section IX-F. That extension is not a separate statistical validation result of this paper; rather, it indicates how the BTB framework can serve as the central preparatory step for full-string replacement work, subject to the same measurement, gauge, breaking-load, and professional judgment constraints emphasized throughout the paper.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author thanks J.D. Grandt Piano Supply Co. for providing bass string ordering data and manufacturing threshold values that anchored the tension framework. The author also acknowledges the practical scale-design tradition represented by Pscale360 and its help documentation, whose generous “With Our Thanks To” spirit reflects the collaborative workshop culture from which this study also benefited.

Claude (Anthropic) and ChatGPT (OpenAI) were used for English-language drafting, editorial organization, and L^AT_EX typesetting assistance in the preparation of this manuscript. The author takes full responsibility for all technical content, mathematical claims, data interpretation, and conclusions presented.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Roberts, *The Calculating Technician*. Kansas City, MO, USA: Piano Technicians Guild Foundation Press, 1990, compiled from articles originally published in the *Piano Technicians Journal* (1979–1981); limited distribution. OCLC 25903112. Digitized copy preserved by the late N. V. Gravagne, RPT: https://www.gravagne.com/NicksPageLegacy/Calculating_Technician_Dave_Roberts_Full.pdf (Internet Archive snapshot, 3 Aug. 2025: https://web.archive.org/web/20250803145640/http://gravagne.com/NicksPageLegacy/Calculating_Technician_Dave_Roberts_Full.pdf).
- [2] S. Wolfenden, *A Treatise on the Art of Pianoforte Construction*. Old Woking, Surrey, England: Unwin Brothers, The Gresham Press, 1916, first edition; reprinted by Gresham Books Ltd in 1975 with 1927 supplement. Available: <https://archive.org/details/treatiseonartofp0000samu>.
- [3] J.D. Grandt Piano Supply Co., “Bass string ordering template,” J.D. Grandt Piano Supply Co., Churchill, Ontario, Canada, 2006, standard industry form for string replacement data, originally issued in July 2006 (Richmond Hill) and confirmed current as of Oct. 2025. The template’s requirement for L , d , and m for notes m_{1p} through m_{1p+2} provides independent corroboration of the scaling transition region analyzed in this study. Available: <https://www.jdgrandt.com>.
- [4] K. Fenner and J. Grossbach, *Praktisches Handbuch der Klavierkonstruktion*, ser. Fachbuchreihe Das Musikinstrument. Frankfurt am Main, Germany: Bochinsky, 2000, vol. 75, comprehensive technical guide on piano design geometry. Available: https://openlibrary.org/books/OL4000527M/Praktisches_Handbuch_der_Klavierkonstruktion.
- [5] A. E. Sanderson, “Apparatus and method for electronically tuning a piano,” Patent US5285711A, Feb. 15, 1994, methodology for inharmonicity-compensated pitch stretch in piano tuning. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US5285711A>.
- [6] Stahl- und Drahtwerk Rösrau GmbH, ““röslau” steel wire for piano strings “blue label”: Technical specifications,” Technical data sheet, 1998, current edition confirmed Sep. 18, 2025. Available: https://www.roeslau-draht.com/fileadmin/user_upload/PDF/Datenblaetter/EN/Roeslau_steel_string_wire_blaue_for_piano_wires.pdf.
- [7] A. H. Benade, *Fundamentals of Musical Acoustics*, 2nd ed. New York: Dover Publications, 1990, second, revised edition. Originally published: Oxford University Press, 1976. [Online]. Available: <https://archive.org/details/fundamentalsofmu0000bena>.
- [8] T. Parsons, *Pscale 360 Help Documentation*, v2.8 ed., Sierra Software Services, 2024, documents tension guideline 200:160:140 lbf (unichord:bichord:trichord), attributed therein to A. E. Sanderson (In-ventronics). Available: <https://www.goptools.com/pshelp.html>.
- [9] S. Paulello, “Music wires: Typogram and selection guide,” Technical data sheet, Sep. 2024, accessed: Sep. 15, 2025. Available: <https://spaulello.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/5-Stephen-Paulello-Music-Wires.pdf>.
- [10] R. E. Overs, “A scale comparison of two semi concert grands,” Overs Pianos, Dec. 2001, first published 4 Dec. 2001; last modified 13 Jan. 2002. Available at <https://www.overspianos.com.au/chrts.html> (Accessed: 2025).
- [11] —, “Overs Grand No. 003—Overhead Image,” 2001, photograph taken prior to exhibition at the PTG National Convention, Reno, Nevada, 2001. Available at <https://www.overspianos.com.au/OS003.html> (Accessed: 2025).

- [12] T. Parsons, “Yamaha model ga1 low tenor string retrofit kit: Pscale360 white paper,” Sierra Software Services, Feb. 2023, collaboration with J.D. Grandt Piano Supply Co.; methodology for addressing scaling deficiencies in the treble-bottom region; original version 2010, revised 2023. Available: https://www.goptools.com/bassretro/ga1retro_2023.pdf.
- [13] H. A. Conklin, “Piano design factors—their influence on tone and acoustics,” in *Five Lectures on the Acoustics of the Piano*. Stockholm: Royal Swedish Academy of Music, 1990, lecture 3. Available online at https://www.speech.kth.se/music/5_lectures/conklin/howdoes.html.